

BSD (back-scattered electron detector) image of sample LYDIT4-5 acquired with a SEM ZEISS EVO 25 + Bruker Quantax XFlash 6 | 30M. Locations of the individual EDX measurements are indicated in orange.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample LYDIT4-5 measurement 1. The amount of calcium detected on the surface is too minor (1.20712 mass % normalised) to indicate a perceptible surface contamination with bone residues.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample LYDIT4-5 measurement 2. The amount of calcium detected on the surface is too minor (0.5491 mass % normalised) to indicate a perceptible surface contamination with bone residues.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample LYDIT4-5 measurement 3. The amount of calcium detected on the surface is too minor (0.704319 mass % normalised) to indicate a perceptible surface contamination with bone residues.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample LYDIT4-5 measurement 4. Neither calcium nor phosphorus have been detected on the surface, indicating that the surface is not contaminated with bone residues.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample LYDIT4-5 measurement 5. The amount of calcium detected on the surface is too minor (2.144528 mass % normalised) to indicate a perceptible surface contamination with bone residues.

Spectrum	Carbon	Oxygen	Sodium	Magnesium	Aluminium	Silicon	Sulfur	Potassium	Calcium	Iron
LYDIT4-5 1	0	0	0.22985	0.45107	4.04572	92.6298		1.43648	1.20712	
LYDIT4-5 2	0	0		0.34537	2.44323	95.7727		0.88963	0.5491	
LYDIT4-5 3	0	0	0.34249	0.66282	4.43996	91.476		1.32343	0.70432	1.05103
LYDIT4-5 4	0	0			0.48642	7.60043	44.9637			46.9495
LYDIT4-5 5	0	0	0.80331	0.96262	6.14371	86.75	0.96348	2.23239	2.14453	

Quantitative results of the EDX analysis of sample LYDIT4-5 in mass % normalised.

BSD (back-scattered electron detector) image of sample FLT4-14 acquired with a SEM ZEISS EVO 25 + Bruker Quantax XFlash 6 | 30M. Locations of the individual EDX measurements are indicated in orange.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample FLT4-14 measurement 1. Neither calcium nor phosphorus have been detected on the surface, indicating that the surface is not contaminated with bone residues.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample FLT4-14 measurement 2. Neither calcium nor phosphorus have been detected on the surface, indicating that the surface is not contaminated with bone residues.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample FLT4-14 measurement 3. Neither calcium nor phosphorus have been detected on the surface, indicating that the surface is not contaminated with bone residues.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample FLT4-14 measurement 4. Neither calcium nor phosphorus have been detected on the surface, indicating that the surface is not contaminated with bone residues.

Results of the EDX analysis of sample FLT4-14 measurement 5. Both calcium (18.10819 mass % normalised) as well as phosphorus (3.518854 mass % normalised) have been detected on the surface. The measurement was taken in a hole, which still contained some bone residues. The area of the surface was not part of use-wear documentations.

Spectrum	Carbon	Oxygen	Sodium	Magnesium	Aluminium	Silicon	Phosphorus	Sulfur	Calcium
FLT4-14 1	0	0			0.18913	99.8109			
FLT4-14 2	0	0			0.12396	99.876			
FLT4-14 3	0	0			0.156	99.844			
FLT4-14 4	0	0				100			
FLT4-14 5	0	0	0.26679	0.42057		75.7109	3.51885	1.97472	18.1082

Quantitative results of the EDX analysis of sample FLT4-14 in mass % normalised.